

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AS A SOURCE OF LIFE AND ITS DEVELOPMENT**Xudoyqulova Shoirra Husanovna**

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Abstract. This article provides a comprehensive overview of emotional intelligence and the ability to differentiate between it, emotions, and a person's ability to manage their emotional states.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, emotion, interaction, social skills, empathy, self-management strategies, motivation.

**ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ – ИСТОЧНИК ЖИЗНИ И ЕГО
РАЗВИТИЕ**

Аннотация. В данной статье подробно рассмотрены эмоциональный интеллект и способность различать эмоции, переживания, а также способность человека управлять своим эмоциональным состоянием.

Ключевые слова: Эмоциональный интеллект, эмоции, взаимодействие, социальные навыки, эмпатия, стратегии самоуправления, мотивация.

Our country has the necessary conditions and opportunities for education and training at the level of world standards, for the realization of the creative potential of our citizens. Based on the new conditions, it is necessary to ensure the continuity and consistency of educational stages, to create a modern methodology of education, to improve and implement state educational standards in accordance with the competency-based approach. In the current period, the relevance of social psychology to all processes taking place in society has also expanded the scope of its applied areas.

The issue of paying serious attention to the understanding, analysis and development of personality psychology has always been one of the leading tasks of socio-economic development in all times and in all countries. At the turn of the 20th century, the science of psychology and its advanced representatives were able to theoretically and scientifically substantiate their next global scientific hypothesis - the viability of a system of psychological services for the individual, and at the same time, for society.

Emotional intelligence (EI) is a person's ability to recognize the emotions, intentions, desires of other people, as well as the ability to manage their own and other people's emotions.

There are 5 characteristics that explain emotional intelligence (EI):

- Self-awareness - the study of oneself, mental and physical characteristics;
- Self-control - the ability to manage one's emotions to achieve goals;
- Social skills - the ability to successfully communicate with other people.
- Empathy - the ability to identify the emotions of others.
- Motivation - the impulse that drives a person to action.

Self-awareness and self-control speak for themselves.

Self-awareness is the process of focusing on one's inner world as a result of self-knowledge and comparison with other people. Social skills and relationship management are aspects of how you interact with other people. A high level of self-awareness can only be achieved by understanding your emotions.

A high level of self-awareness indicates that a person is not afraid to make mistakes and will behave differently in the future.

Self-management is the ability to act or refrain from acting, it is the ability to use knowledge of your emotions to decide what to say and do, and to actively resolve the situation.

Self-management strategies:

- create a list of emotions and logical explanations;
- postpone resolving the situation for a day, a week or a month, this will allow you to "digest" the situation before moving forward,
- laugh and smile more;
- talk to someone who is not related to your problem,
- learn to learn valuable lessons from emotional communication with each person. Social sensitivity is the ability to accurately perceive the emotions of other people and understand what is happening to them.

Listening and observing are two of the most important elements of social perception. Social sensitivity allows you to maintain concentration and perceive the most important information coming from the interlocutor. Relationship management is the ability to use your ability to perceive emotions (your own and those experienced by others) to effectively establish interaction.

Relationship management is the connections that a person forms with other people over time. Strong relationships are the result of how well you understand people, how you interact with them, and how you share a history with them. The weaker a person's connection with other people, the more difficult it is to convey their thoughts to them.

In every relationship, even the most obvious, you need to find advantages. Emotional intelligence consists of four main abilities:

- self-awareness,
- self-management,

- social sensitivity,
- relationship management.

Emotional intelligence is one of the main factors in achieving the goals set by a person. We have consistently found that EQ plays a significant role in shaping a successful, healthy and productive personal life.

It is also important to form emotional intelligence in the family. Properly organizing the style of the family environment requires special responsibility.

Sit at the same level as your child, take deep breaths, relax and concentrate. The child should feel that you are serious about his problem and are ready to devote your attention to it.

Your time. When the child tells you about his feelings, show him that you hear him and are interested in him.

Let's give an example: Example: A child got lost in a large store and his mother is very worried. After some time, a store employee finds the upset child and helps him meet with her.

Incorrect answer: It is considered to increase the child's sense of danger by speaking harsh words to his personality. In this case, the danger does not disappear in either the child or the mother. The child's feeling: Fear.

Correct answer: "You must have been afraid, I was afraid too. Come here, I will hold your hand. We'll talk about what happened later..." Emotions are mental processes that occur in the form of experiences and reflect the personal significance and assessment of external and internal situations for human life. Emotions characterize human needs and the objects to which they are directed. The meaning of emotions is a warning about the destructive nature of any factor.

Emotions are a mechanism for regulating the functional state of the body and human activity.

The dual nature of emotions.

1. The subjectivity of emotions.
2. The connection of emotions with physiological processes.

According to the scientist D. Goleman, it is only in early childhood that it is easy to correct a person's emotional development. In most cases, the system that regulates our emotions completes its formation by the age of 15-16, and later its correction is very difficult and expensive. This should be paid special attention to when raising and forming a mature personality.

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